

HISTORY OF MEDICINAL PLANTS

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The forests of Uzbekistan are rich in various medicinal trees and shrubs. Human life is inextricably linked with the world of plants, because they fed, clothed, treated, built, and served as a source of medicinal and technical raw materials. Medicinal plants have been known to humanity since ancient times.

Plants were widely used not only as food, but also as a source of biologically active substances. There is evidence that medicinal plants were used for medicinal purposes in the Sumerian civilization 5000 years ago. Medicinal plants have served as the only source of medicines for long historical periods. From the Middle Ages, many scientific works on the description of medicinal plants and their use in improving human health have reached us.

Our compatriot Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), who made a great contribution to the development of world medical science, wrote more than 20 scientific works on medical issues. The scientist created the 5-volume work "Al-Konun" ("The Laws of Medicine") based on his experiences during 20 years of medical practice. This work served not only Arabs, but also European doctors as a guide for centuries. The book contains information about more than 500 medicinal plants and more than 40 medicinal products prepared from them.

This famous work of the scientist was translated and published in many European languages, and it was reprinted 16 times in Latin.

V.Dushenkov, I. According to Raskin, in Karaganda, 20,000 different simple molecular substances have been isolated from plants. Therefore, in the following decades, the interest in medicinal plants is increasing again, because the medicines prepared on the basis of their raw materials - vitamins, biologically active compounds and mineral substances - have a very effective effect on the human body.

From 1981, 43 of the 847 simple molecular drugs used in medical practice are considered to be natural compounds, and 232 are the properties of natural compounds. 262 out of 572 new medicinal products are related to natural compounds. It is known that approximately 50% of drugs produced in

pharmaceutical enterprises worldwide are made from raw materials of medicinal plants.

In particular, 77% of medicinal preparations used for the treatment and prevention of cardiovascular diseases, 74% of medicinal preparations used for the prevention and treatment of liver and gastrointestinal diseases, 73% of expectorant drugs, 60% of anti-inflammatory drugs are based on medicinal plant raw materials. in development. Currently, according to the information of the International Organization for Food and Agriculture (FAO), in Karaganda, more than 50,000 medicinal plants are used for medicinal purposes in the whole world.

The use of representatives of local flora for treatment purposes is high in Southeast Asian countries, this figure is 20% in India and 19% in China. In the pharmacopoeias of Japan, Germany and other European countries, preparations made on the basis of raw medicinal plants occupy a large place. About 4,500 species of tall plants are distributed in the territory of Uzbekistan, and about 1,200 of them have medicinal properties. Currently, 112 types of medicinal plants are allowed to be used in official medicine in our Republic, and 80% of them are naturally growing plants.

Medicinal plants in Uzbekistan include pomegranate, achchikmia, almond, medicinal gulkhairi, walnut, jag-jag, zubturum, frankincense, ytsigek, omonkora, pistachio tree, sachratki, choyut, shildirbosh, shirminiya, shuvok, yantok, kizilcha, kakukut, zirk, namatak and used more than others. Alkaloids are obtained from bitter gourd - paxicarnin, from yarrow - garmin, from yarrow - anabazin, from omonkora - galantamine, and from syldirbosh - spherophysin. Pomegranate pods are used to prepare gijja haidavchi pelterin tanat and extract.

Medicinal gulkhairi preparations are used as expectorants and softeners, jag-jag and lagochilus drugs are used as anti-diarrheal drugs, and pistachio bujgun and choyut drugs are used to treat gastrointestinal diseases. Medicinal plants are divided into alkaloidal, glycosidic, essential oil, and vitamin plants depending on the composition of their active substances. Depending on their pharmacological properties, they are divided into groups of medicinal plants that are calming, anti-aggressive, hypnotic, have an effect on the cardiovascular system, monitor the central nervous system, reduce blood pressure, and other medicinal plants.

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